

Impact of Corporate Sustainability Reports on Working Capital Performance: Application of Tourism Companies¹

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Abstract

The efficiency and productivity of the working capital required for businesses to carry out their daily activities are very important. Excess working capital indicates that there are unused assets, and low working capital indicates that there are insufficient assets. While excess working capital does not cause serious problems for the business, low working capital causes problems in paying short-term debts. The fact that businesses have high amounts of assets and sales does not indicate that the business is successful. If the sales made on credit cannot be collected on time and unnecessary payments are made, it will not be able to make payments such as goods prices, personnel wages, bank loans, taxes. This will lead the business to failure. In recent years, businesses and society have been seriously negatively affected due to the unnecessary and improper use of production and natural resources. For this reason, the United Nations and many other institutions/organizations have determined studies and criteria on sustainability. It has become mandatory for companies to publish sustainability reports within the framework of GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) principles, and for tourism businesses in Turkey to publish sustainability reports within the framework of the Turkey Sustainable Tourism Industry Criteria (TR-I). The study aims to reveal how the compliance rates with sustainability criteria affect the efficiency and productivity of the working capital of businesses. The study revealed that the sustainable

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compliance rates of tourism companies in BIST positively affect the working capital-related rates and income. In other words, the corporate governance, cultural-environmental and socio-economic activities of tourism companies in terms of sustainability cause the working capital of the enterprises to be used more effectively.

Keywords

Working Capital, Sustainability, Tourism Businesses.

1. Introduction

Working capital is defined as the capital required for the normal daily activities of businesses without using their fixed assets (Stoltz et al, 2007: 305). Therefore, the investments made by the business to achieve short-term goals in maximizing its value constitute the working capital of the business. Gross working capital shows the current assets, while net working capital shows the difference between current assets and short-term liabilities. Working capital is also called business capital. Working capital is important for the business to operate at high capacity, produce, expand its business volume, pay its short-term liabilities and run the business profitably and efficiently (Akgüç, 1998, p. 201). Working capital also shows the accounts with high liquidity among the current assets of the business (Brigham and Houston, 2007, p.63). These accounts are cash and cash equivalents, securities, trade receivables and stock accounts. Adequate working capital is needed for businesses to continue their activities continuously and to control or reduce risks that may arise in paying short-term debts (Toraman and Sönmez, 2015, p.23). The most important element that ensures that businesses survive in crises or negative situations that occur at sectoral, national or international levels is again sufficient working capital (Ganesan, 2007). We see that most of the bankruptcies of businesses are due to insufficient working capital.

Due to the risks and characteristics of the tourism sector, it is not always possible to protect working capital in the best way. For this reason, we see that businesses operating in the tourism sector carry out other sector activities together within the same business. For example, they carry out activities such as tourism and trade, tourism and export. They aim to eliminate the working capital deficiency that may occur with other activities in periods when the tourism sector is not doing well. Working capital is also one of the elements of keeping the financial performance of the business high (Shin, 1998). In order to have an effective working capital, the most appropriate current asset structure can be created by minimizing the risks caused by cash insufficiencies and minimizing the costs while meeting the financing needs (Ata and Buğan, 2016). With effective working capital management, the financial performance of the business will increase, short-term debts will be paid and it will play an important role in maximizing the welfare of the shareholders. As it is known, most of the companies that go bankrupt are due to having problems in paying short-term debts despite having sufficient sales volume. The mortgage crisis that affected the whole world in 2008 was mainly due to the non-collection of receivables and non-payment of debts.

The performance of an accommodation business can be summarized as the main profitability determinants, such as creditors, owners, managers and employees, as well as the characteristics of the hotel, the location of the hotel and the competitive environment (Lado-Sestayo et al., 2017).

The ability of companies to achieve their goals in the long term and their stable growth is related to the sustainability activities of the companies to some extent. We see that the concept of sustainability is used intensively in the economy and companies. We see that the concept of sustainability is used in many areas such as sustainable management, sustainable development, sustainable marketing, sustainable finance, sustainable production, sustainable tourism, sustainable investment and many others. Sustainability is a concept that includes elements such as environmental impact, economic indicators and social welfare (Finkbeiner, et al., 2010).

Economic activities and developments are based on the demand-supply balance. Businesses still produce based on customer demand, despite the fact that it is harmful to the environment and health. When we look at it from this perspective, the sustainability of the production or the product sold is not considered much. In evaluating the success of companies, values such as how much a commercial enterprise sells, how much occupancy rate a hotel business has, how much export revenue an exporter earns are used. Therefore, vital issues such as environment and health remain in the background in production/sales. Although the competent authorities have made some legal regulations to ensure sustainability, we see that they are not taken into consideration much. Health professionals state that most of the products sold in markets are unhealthy (WHO, 2020).

Due to unplanned investments made in the past to increase the welfare level of the society, production for sales purposes only, environmental tourism activities beyond capacity and other reasons, there is a shortage of many natural resources needed. It shows that natural resources, which have been consumed in large quantities since human history, have deteriorated several times in the last 40 years (wikipedia, 2016). Since the industrial revolution, the environment has been negatively affected by the world population growth. Deforestation, environmental pollution, and climate change continue to increase (ethw.org, 2022) Sustainability can be defined as performing an activity or work in a way that will ensure that it is used and utilized in later periods. If the work is a production or service, it requires that the materials used are purchased, personnel are employed, services provided to customers, and other activities do not harm the environment, health, personnel, the sector and state in which it operates. One of the basic principles of accounting, "continuity of business", also expresses this. In other words, businesses are not established and act only for a certain period of time. They should act and decide in a way that will continue their activities regardless of a certain period of time. Considering that businesses will continue their activities for a long time, they should consume the natural environment in which they are located and the materials they receive from the natural environment at a level that will be used continuously. When raw materials and energy cannot be provided continuously for a business, it will not be possible to produce or sell. However, sustainability should be evaluated not only from the environmental but also from economic, political, legal, health, and consumer perspectives. In addition, sustainability should carry the concept of all parties constituting the business, consumer, public and society acting together.

The basis of the idea of sustainability is to leave the use of economic, social and environmental resources to today and future societies and to observe justice. Sustainability is expressed as the capacity of societies to meet the resources they have in the future without harming the needs of individuals (Mckeown et al., 2002). When we look at it in terms of sustainable finance, it is a discipline that ensures that financial resources are used by taking into account environmental, social and governance criteria in order to create a positive social impact (Qi and Li, 2020). A company can implement its concrete steps regarding sustainability with its commitment to the principles of transparency, fairness, accountability and responsibility of corporate governance.

Companies, sustainability, financial and non-financial reports to share sustainability information with shareholders. These activities of companies are also an institutional tool for solving sustainable development problems (Rosati, 2019). These reports also increase transparency with the impact of companies on sustainable development and ultimately lead to an increase in the financial performance of companies. In recent years, the relationship between corporate sustainability and company performance has begun to appear in the literature and has begun to positively affect the financial and non-financial values of companies.

In recent years, companies have been required to implement the 2030 criteria for Sustainable Development established by the United Nations, along with basic goals such as making profits and increasing capital income (United Nations, 2015). In this context, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have been determined. companies need to adapt or transform their methods, production, marketing activities and processes to ensure the implementation of green and socially responsible business models. Only in this way can companies' activities be integrated with society and adopted by society.

First of all, environmental sustainability practices focus on energy efficiency and water saving measures. Many studies conducted in luxury hotels show that environmental practices such as energy efficiency, water consumption reduction, waste management and carbon emission reduction are successfully implemented (Ness, Urbel-Piirsalu, Anderberg and Olsson, 2007). There must be a physical environment or space for tourism activities to be carried out. Therefore, the environment is positively or negatively affected by tourism activities (Usal, 1998).

Measuring working capital performance in accommodation businesses is quite complex in terms of influencing factors, sector structure, sales level. In recent years, corporate sustainability practices, market orientation, service quality have made both financial and non-financial measurements more complex among the main factors affecting financial performance in accommodation businesses (Yang, 2021).

In Turkey, the shares of 12 tourism companies are traded on Borsa İstanbul 'BİST'. Within the scope of sustainability, the sustainability practices of tourism companies are important due to the negative effects of tourism on the environment. For this purpose, a study was conducted to examine the environmental, social and economic activities of tourism companies that publish sustainability reports within the framework of the principles of the non-profit organization GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) and the Turkey Sustainable Tourism Industry Criteria (TR-I) and to reveal the changes in the last 7 years and how they are reflected in the company's working capital performance. The tourism sector, which was

selected as the study area, also has its own characteristics. The concentration of income in certain periods, while the emergence of expenses throughout the year, negatively affects the determination of working capital and the provision of liquidity. Considering that the tourism sector will be different from businesses in other sectors due to the risks and characteristics it carries, this study was analyzed using the ratio analysis method in the measurement of the working capital efficiency of publicly held enterprises in the tourism sector. There are many studies on working capital in the literature, but no studies on the efficiency of working capital in the tourism sector were found. The annual data of 12 companies registered in BIST between 2017 and 2023 were used in the study. The data was obtained from the Public Disclosure Platform (KAP).

2. Literature

Financial performance analysis in accommodation establishments is a multifaceted subject that encompasses various determinants and influencing factors. Since tourism activities directly concern the environment, the relationship between environmental and economic performance has been widely discussed in the literature for the last decade (Wagner and Schaltegger, 2004). However, some studies have shown that greening is beneficial for companies in terms of cost reduction, productivity, innovation and economic performance (Iraldo et al., 2009; Koo et al., 2014).

Studies show that there is a significant and increasing relationship between sustainability and green practices and company financial performance. However, many studies have also shown that sustainability practices reduce economic performance due to their costs.

Studies on working capital and sustainability in recent years are as follows: - Sakarya (2008) and Yücel and Kurt (2002), focused on effective working capital in their studies by finding the cash conversion period with data such as stock turnover rate, average collection period of receivables and payment period for short-term resources.

- Kendirli and Çankaya (2016), analyzed the relationship between working capital and profitability using the data of tourism companies operating in Borsa Istanbul (BIST) between 2010 and 2014 and found a positive and significant relationship between working capital and asset profitability.

- Akoto et al. (2013), examined the relationship between working capital and profitability on 13 manufacturing enterprises registered on the Ghana Stock Exchange, and using data from 2005-2009 of these enterprises, asset profitability was determined as the dependent variable, Cash Conversion Period (CCP), Receivables Collection Period (RCP), Stock supply duration (SSD), Debt Payment period (DPP) and current rate were determined as independent variables. As a result of panel data analysis, a positive relationship was determined between CCP, current ratio, business size, current asset turnover rate and profitability.

- Rahman, Abdul (2023), Working capital performance, use of current assets and working capital efficiency on automobile manufacturing companies were measured using the regression method and statistically significant results were obtained. It was concluded that effective working capital increases sales with existing assets.

- Jayarathne (2014), examined the relationship between working capital and profitability in his study on manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka. It has been revealed that profitability can be higher if working capital is managed effectively.
- Tirado et al. (2019) showed that factors such as cost reduction and environmental concerns are important when hotel managers implement water saving measures in hotels in Mallorca.
- Olya et al. (2020) showed in a study conducted in the Kazakhstan hotel industry that social and environmental sustainability activities have positive effects on guest satisfaction and loyalty.
- Irani et al. (2022) showed in a study conducted in green hotels in Turkey that green human resources practices increase environmental performance and encourage employees' participation in sustainable activities.
- Kasim et al. (2014) showed in a study conducted in hotels in Macau that hotels make significant efforts to increase energy efficiency and implement energy saving and environmental protection programs.
- Lado et al. (2018) found that corporate sustainability performance significantly increases investment efficiency in investment decisions.
- Pano, A(2019), In their research on small and medium-sized Italian hotels, it was observed that the businesses adopted a balanced performance measurement system that included traditional financial indicators such as net profit, return on investment, return on sales, revenue per room, occupancy rate and cost efficiency ratios.
- Friede et al. (2015) and Albertini (2013) revealed that ESG positively affects operational, financial and market performance in the manufacturing sector.
- Buallay (2019) stated in a study that ESG positively affects operational, financial and market performance in the manufacturing sector and negatively in the banking sector.
- Varzaru et al. (2021) revealed that sustainability practices lead to innovation performance, which in turn increases financial and market performance.
- According to KPMG's report, there has been a substantial increase in the adoption of sustainability reports in India (KPMG, 2020).
- Tan et al. (2017), in a study on the London hotel industry, stated that liquidity, capitalization, debt and employee costs are the main determinants of profitability.
- Lado et al. (2017) stated that the profitability performance of a hotel business depends on creditors, owners, managers and employees, as well as hotel features, hotel location and competitive environment.
- Pham, D. C., Do, T., Doan and Et Al (2021), in a study on companies in Sweden, revealed a positive relationship between sustainability practices and financial performance.
- Yilmaz (2021), in a study on companies in BRICS countries, revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between sustainability performance and financial performance, while environmental and social individual scores are not significant.
- Sreepriya et al. (2022), in their study reveals that GRI compliance moderates the relationship between sustainability disclosures and firm value, and firm value increases when the company adopts GRI in sustainability reporting.

- Lehenchuk et al(2023), in their study on businesses in the food and textile sectors in Turkey, found that sustainability reporting was not positively related to the financial performance measures of Turkish companies.

- Deloof (2003) conducted a regression analysis on 1,009 companies operating in Belgium during the period 1992-1996 and found a strong negative relationship between gross profitability and cash conversion cycle, receivables collection period and inventory holding period.

3. Corporate Sustainability and Tourism

People use natural resources to continue their lives. The fact that natural resources are limited and used rapidly causes the resources to fall to insufficient levels and even face complete depletion. On the other hand, the rapid increase in tourism activities based on the natural environment causes natural resources to be depleted or damaged more rapidly. Environmental, social and political conflicts have emerged with tourism activities. This has made it necessary to make some applications and regulations. Sustainability practices come first among these. Necessary regulations have been made to minimize the negative effects of tourism and continue to be made. Regulations regarding sustainability are made in two ways. One is related to the use of the natural environment and the other is regulations regarding the applications within the companies themselves.

Sustainable tourism; Sustainability is very important in tourism as tourism can continue healthily in regions where tourism is intense and the income obtained from tourism is stable and the benefits it will provide to the region (Göktepe, 2011; Keleş, 2003).

Many legal regulations have been made worldwide for sustainability practices to be implemented primarily by large companies and all institutions and organizations.

It has become mandatory for businesses that generate more than 150 million Euros in revenue in the EU and non-EU companies that have a branch/large company or a listed SME with more than 40 million Euros in revenue in the EU to publish their 2028 financial year report in 2029.

In addition, the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) calendar has been determined, which is estimated to include an average of 50,000 businesses as of January 1, 2024. The aim of CSRD is to provide stakeholders with better data on corporate sustainability. To understand how the CSRD impacts business, it is helpful to start by looking at the objectives of this legislation.

Sustainability practices in the accommodation sector, strategies and practices adopted to increase the environmental, social and economic performance of accommodation businesses can provide significant benefits in terms of reducing the environmental impacts of businesses, reducing their costs and increasing customer satisfaction (Pereira, et Al, 2021).

Graph.1. Sustainability in the Tourism Sector.

Reference: Taken from Amazing Borneo Tours

There are many hotels in the world that operate in line with the idea of sustainability and with real green energy. In Turkey, although the number of hotels has increased, the number is very few. In recent years, both travelers and travel agencies have started to prefer hotels that are environmentally friendly, such as emissions, wastewater, water and electricity consumption. This has made it mandatory for hotels to implement sustainability practices.

4. Methodology

4.1. Purpose of the Study:

The purpose of the study is to measure whether corporate sustainability reports have an effect on the adequacy and efficiency measurement of working capital of tourism companies traded on BIST. Working capital is a capital required for companies to carry out their activities. Without sufficient and efficient working capital, it is not possible for a company to grow and be profitable, and annual profits alone do not measure the efficiency and success of the company. Working capital adequacy was measured using liquidity ratios related to working capital, Revenues/Working Capital ratio and companies' revenues in the ratio analysis method. Therefore, the study tried to find out whether sustainability performance has an effect on the efficiency and adequacy of companies' working capital. Ratio analysis is a financial analysis method used to measure the profitability, efficiency and efficiency levels of companies, and since working capital accounts related to current assets are used in the ratio analysis, the current ratio, liquidity ratio and cash ratio used to measure the efficiency and efficiency of current assets were found and the sustainability compliance criteria compliance rates were compared and analyzed.

4.2. Method of the Study:

The study was conducted using data from 12 tourism companies whose shares are traded on Borsa Istanbul (BIST). However, since data from previous years belonging to some companies could not be accessed, data from 9 companies for the years 2017-2023 were used to determine the liquidity ratios used in the effectiveness and efficiency of working capital and their compliance with sustainability criteria. The companies have sustainability reports for the years 2022 and 2023, while the sustainability compliance status for the period 2017-2021 was taken from the companies' activity reports. The corporate sustainability reports published by the companies were evaluated in line with the principles of the Turkey Sustainable Tourism Industry Criteria (TR-I) and GRI (Global Reporting Initiative). Since the Turkey Sustainable Tourism Industry Criteria (TR-I) are published according to the first stage of sustainability in Turkey, the analysis was conducted according to these reports.

Table.1. Tourism Companies Included in the Research.

The code of the companies on the Stock Exchange	Company Name
PKENT	Petrokent Turizm A.Ş.
AVTUR	Avrasya Petrol ve Turistik Tesisler Yatırımlar A.Ş.
AYCES	Altın Yunus Çeşme Turistik Tesisler A.Ş.
DOCO	DO & CO AG
MAALT	Marmaris Altinyunus Turistik Tesisleri A.Ş.
MARTI	Martı Otel İşletmeleri A.Ş.
PKENT	Petrokent Turizm A.Ş.
TEKTU	Tek-Art İnşaat Ticaret Turizm Sanayi ve Yatırımlar A.Ş.
ULAŞ	Ulaşlar Turizm Yatırımları ve Dayanıklı Tüketim Malları Ticaret Pazarlama A.Ş.
ETİLR	Etiler Gıda ve Ticari Yatırımlar Sanayi ve Ticaret A.Ş.

The following table shows the variables used to reveal the relationship between the companies' compliance rates with sustainability criteria and the rates measuring the effectiveness and efficiency of working capital.

The dependent variables were determined as the rates used without measuring working capital, and the independent variables were determined as the compliance rates with sustainability criteria.

Table.2. Variables of the Research.

Variables	Rations	Formula
Dependent Variables	Working Capital Ratios - Current Ratio - Liquidity Ratio	- Current Ratio = Current Assets/Short Term Liabilities

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cash Ratio - Income/Net Working Capital Ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Liquidity Ratio = Current Assets – Stocks/Short Term Liabilities - Cash Ratio = Current Assets-(Trade Receivables+Stocks)/Short Term Liabilities - Income/Net working capital ratio
Independent Variables	Sustainability Compliance Criteria	Sustainability Compatibility Numbers
Sustainable Management	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sustainability Management System 2. Legal compliance 3. Reporting and communication 4. Staff participation 5. Customer experience 6. Correct promotion 7. Buildings and infrastructure 8. Water and property rights on land 9. Information and interpretation 10. Destination participation 	Analysis was conducted using the compliance numbers of companies with the Türkiye Sustainable Tourism Industry Criteria (TR-I) and GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) criteria in their sustainability reports.
Cultural And Environmental	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Protection of Water and Other Natural Resources 2. Environmentally Sensitive Purchasing 3. Efficient Purchasing 4. Energy Saving 5. Water Saving 6. Pollution Reduction 7. Greenhouse Gas Emissions 8. Transportation 9. Wastewater 10. Solid Waste 11. Protection of Biodiversity, Ecosystems and Landscapes 12. Cultural Interactions 13. Protection of Cultural Heritage 14. Protection of Artifacts 	
Socio-Economic	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Support for local people/regional people 2. Local/regional employment 3. Local/regional purchasing 4. Local/regional entrepreneurs 5. Exploitation and harassment 	

	6. Equal opportunities 7. Decent work 8. Community service activities 9. Local/regional livelihoods 10. Business ethics	
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In the literature, we see that different rates are generally used as dependent variables for similar studies. These studies include Enquist et al. (2014), Sharma and Kumar (2011), Raheman and Nasr (2007). Akoto et al. (2013). In addition to these studies, rates such as company market value and gross profitability ratio have been used as dependent variables. Toraman and Sönmez (2015), Napompech (2012) can be given as examples of these studies.

Since the aim of our study is to measure the effect of compliance rates in sustainability reports on working capital, the rates used to measure the effectiveness of working capital were used as dependent variables, and compliance rates to sustainability reports were used as independent variables.

Accordingly, the research model is as follows.

$$CR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SM + \beta_2 SCE + \beta_3 SSE + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$LR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SM + \beta_2 SCE + \beta_3 SSE + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$NR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SM + \beta_2 SCE + \beta_3 SSE + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$INWCR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SM + \beta_2$$

$$SCE + \beta_3 SSE + \epsilon_{it}$$

CR= Current Ratio

LR= Liquidity Ratio

NR= Cash Ratio

INWCR= Income/ Net Working Capital Ratio

SM = Sustainable Management

SCE= sustainable cultural-environment

SSE= sustainable socio-economic.

Ratio Analysis

Liquidity ratios are used to measure whether the working capital has the ability to pay short-term debts.

Liquidity ratios also measure the effectiveness and efficiency of current assets.

These are;

I. Current ratio: The current ratio expresses the ability of the company's current assets to pay short-term debts. The sum of all current assets is used to calculate the current ratio.

Current ratio = Current Assets/Short-Term Foreign Resources.

II. Liquidity ratio: The liquidity ratio is found by subtracting stocks from current assets and dividing them by short-term foreign resources. In other words, it shows the solvency of current assets other than stocks and short-term foreign resources.

Liquidity Ratio = (Current Assets-Stocks)/Short-Term Foreign Resources.

III. Cash ratio: The cash ratio is an important indicator in evaluating the solvency of the company with its cash and cash equivalents. The higher the cash ratio, the higher the company's ability to pay its short-term debts.

Cash Ratio = Cash and cash equivalents/Short-Term Foreign Resources.

When examining liquidity ratios, the three ratios should be examined together and according to the sector status in the relevant year. For example, it can be negative in terms of current ratio and positive in terms of liquidity ratio. Here, liquidity and cash ratio are more decisive. If companies have problems in collecting and selling their receivables, it is more decisive to measure how short-term debts will be paid.

The liquidity ratios used to measure the ability to pay short-term debts and the adequacy of working capital of the tourism companies included in the research for the periods of 2019-2023 were calculated and are given in the table below.

The income/working capital ratio is used to measure how income changes working capital. Income is divided by the net working capital of the relevant period. It is also widely used in the purchase of company shares regardless of whether they are cheap or expensive.

Table.3. Working Capital Ratios and Income of Companies.

		AVTUR	AYCES	ETİLR	MAALT	PKENT	TEKTU	ULA ₺	MARTI	DOCO
Current Ratio	2017	3.45	1,52	2,65	8,52	0,42	1,84	2,68	3,52	1,66
	2018	2.98	1,05	1,54	7,54	0,97	1,26	3,20	2,68	1,95
	2019	2,52	0,53	0,19	15,54	1,36	1,36	3,50	2,10	1,36
	2020	6,02	0,21	13,75	16,64	1,00	1,00	2,12	1,60	2,10
	2021	6,23	1,11	5,68	10,91	2,13	2,13	4,50	3,50	2,80
	2022	5,75	1,31	1,42	2,04	1,42	1,42	1,87	2,58	2,10
	2023	11,41	1,28	1,21	16,65	1,05	1,05	2,82	2,94	1,98
Liquidity Ratio	2017	3,54	4,02	1,25	5,20	0,41	2,20	2,10	3,50	1,49
	2018	4,20	4,47	1,26	1,68	0,95	1,10	1,15	1,25	1,74
	2019	2,51	0,48	0,18	15,54	1,28	1,28	2,63	1,82	1,27
	2020	6,02	0,20	13,60	16,64	0,97	0,97	1,61	1,24	2,00
	2021	5,02	1,07	5,00	10,91	2,07	2,07	3,47	3,12	2,65
	2022	4,74	1,26	1,38	2,04	1,31	1,31	1,12	1,58	2,00
	2023	11,35	1,21	1,00	16,64	0,93	0,93	1,87	2,12	1,85
	2017	3,74	1,97	0,65	0,80	0,22	1,25	1,25	1,42	0,75
	2018	6,79	1,40	0,52	14,63	0,64	0,50	1,80	2,42	1,03
	2019	3,81	0,36	0,16	15,54	0,23	0,23	2,23	1,75	0,85

Cash Ratio	2020	5,13	0,18	13,60	16,62	0,20	0,20	1,61	1,05	1,26
	2021	5,02	0,97	2,87	10,90	1,39	1,39	1,02	1,04	1,24
	2022	4,74	2,97	0,39	2,04	0,96	0,96	1,12	1,06	1,02
	2023	8,79	1,10	0,33	16,63	0,53	0,53	1,65	2,12	0,85
INWCR	2017	3.65	1,58	5,54	4,85	5,60	1,52	0	0,37	7,59
	2018	2.80	1,85	4,65	3,86	4,68	1,84	0	0,52	5,41
	2019	2,60	1,63	4,87	4,35	5,32	1,12	0		5,90
	2020	3,54	1,54	3,85	3,12	4,25	0,65	0		1,15
	2021	3,10	2,12	3,96	3,45	4,10	0,45	0		2,71
	2022	3,85	2,65	4,25	4,65	3,95	0,28	0		5,86
	2023	2,65	2,80	3,95	3,85	4,05	0,39	0		2,16
Revenue	2017	3,204,5 89	25.468. 376	4.059.8 79	6,385,3 00	36,671, 865	18.018. 364	0	58.176. 401	3.714.5 30.
	2018	4,936,3 69	37.203. 528	5.201.7 62	4,524,7 51	76,412, 502	33.269. 424	0	120.564 .633	5.109.7 33
	2019	5.262.9 93	47.452. 117	4.014.4 84	4.885.8 26	99.817. 481	48.028. 153	0	120.564 .633	6.091.2 09.134
	2020	3.137.1 67	22.003. 994	2.394.7 44	4.915.5 33	35.228. 542	20.888. 764	0	151.785 .037	2.176.7 86.479
	2021	3.511.8 37	63.099. 863	29.229. 424	4.878.3 55	108.41 6.754	41.122. 080	0	65.695. 295	14.712, 710
	2022	10.988. 922	195.53 0.821	281.31 6.444	9.351.2 44	307.85 0.317	87.118. 565	0	132.485 .588	29.612, 460
	2023	11.584. 923	223.41 1.223	330.65 3.245	6.176.9 96	656.48 1.843	86.469. 251	0	359.947 .910	478,120 ,000

When we look at the liquidity ratios of companies, we see that they generally have high ratios. The values obtained in terms of working capital's ability and adequacy to pay short-term debts show that the H4 hypothesis is accepted. In terms of current ratio, AVTUR company has the highest value with a ratio of 11.41 and AYCES company has the lowest value with a ratio of 0.21. Although it is generally considered normal for the current ratio to be around 2, it is also considered normal for this value to be lower in publicly traded companies and in some periods. The real determining value is the ability to pay short-term debts in periods when sales slow down or stop and receivables cannot be collected. Therefore, liquidity and cash ratio are more decisive. In general, it is considered normal for the liquidity ratio to be around 1 and the cash ratio to be around 0.20. When we look at these ratios, AYCES has the lowest ratio with a liquidity ratio of 0.20 in 2020, and MAALT company has the highest ratio with a

ratio of 16.64 in 2020. 2020 was a year when the covid-19 virus was effective. During this period, the activities of many tourism companies came to a halt due to travel restrictions. Despite this, it shows that AYCES company's all rates except 2020 are normal, meaning that they will not have any debt payment problems. Of course, the fact that the rates are too high is also considered a problem. Having a high working capital indicates that they have more current assets than necessary and that working capital is not used efficiently and effectively. Liquidity and cash ratios were high in many companies included in the research. For example, the liquidity ratio was 11.35 in AVTUR company and 16.64 in MAALT company in 2023. High ratios like this indicate that working capital is not used effectively.

It is observed that the current, liquidity and cash ratios in ULAŞ, MARTI and DOCO companies are within the normal range.

Sustainability Criteria

Turkey Sustainable Tourism Industry Criteria (TR-I) was created to ensure the sustainable growth of the Turkish tourism sector and to develop a common culture for Turkish tourism with the participation of all parties. TR-I was prepared to be implemented by accommodation facilities and tour operators and TR-I is grouped under four main headings. Sustainable management; socio-economic impacts; cultural impacts and environmental impacts are classified as follows. In this study, the number of elements that companies comply with in their published sustainability reports was evaluated by considering this classification and GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) principles.

The table below shows how much companies comply with the Turkey Sustainable Tourism Industry Criteria and GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) principles together with their sub-components based on the corporate sustainability reports published by the companies. The data was taken from the sustainability reports published by the companies.

Table.4. Number Of Companies' Compliance (Positive) In The Corporate Sustainability Report

SUSTAINABILITY CRITERIA	YEARS	AVTUR	AYCES	ETİLR	MAALT	PKENT	TEKTU	ULAŞ	MARTI	DOCO
SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT 1. Sustainability Management System	2017	1	5	1	4	3	0	1	1	4
	2018	2	5	1	4	4	1	2	2	3
	2019	2	6	1	5	5	1	0	2	3
	2020	2	6	1	6	5	1	0	2	3
	2021	2	7	1	7	6	1	1	3	4
2. Legal compliance	2022	2	8	1	7	7	1	0	3	4
3. Reporting and communication										
4. Staff participation										
5. Customer experience	2023	3	10	1	9	7	3	3	5	5

6. Correct promotion										
7. Buildings and infrastructure										
8. Water and property rights on land										
9. Information and interpretation										
10. Destination participation										
CULTURAL AND ENVIRONMENTL	2017	1	6	1	2	4	2	1	2	4
	2018	2	7	2	2	5	3	1	3	5
1. Protection of Water and Other Natural Resources	2019	2	10	1	1	5	2	0	5	6
	2020	3	10	2	1	5	2	0	5	6
	2021	3	11	2	2	6	3	1	6	7
2. Environmentally Sensitive Purchasing	2022	3	12	3	3	7	3	1	7	7
3. Efficient Purchasing										
4. Energy Saving										
5. Water Saving										
6. Pollution Reduction										
7. Greenhouse Gas Emissions										
8. Transportation										
9. Wastewater										
10. Solid Waste										
11. Protection of Biodiversity, Ecosystems and Landscapes										
12. Cultural Interactions										
13. Protection of Cultural Heritage	2023	3	13	0	4	7	4	1	8	7

14. Protection of Artifacts											
SOCIO-ECONOMIC	2017	4	6	2	6	5	6	1	5	6	
	2018	5	6	1	5	4	6	2	4	6	
	1. Support for local people/regional people	2019	6	7	2	8	5	7	1	6	7
		2020	6	8	1	8	5	7	1	6	8
		2021	7	8	2	9	6	8	2	5	9
	2. Local/regional employment	2022	8	9	0	9	7	10	2	6	8
	3. Local/regional purchasing										
	4. Local/regional entrepreneurs										
	5. Exploitation and harassment										
	6. Equal opportunities										
7. Decent work											
8. Community service activities											
9. Local/regional livelihoods											
10. Business ethics	2023	9	10	0	10	7	11	0	6	9	
Total		76	167	26	111	115	83	14	94	119	

It is seen that Altın Yunus Çeşme Touristic Facilities Inc., which meets all the criteria of Sustainable Management, cultural, environmental and socio-economic, has the highest performance. On the other hand, Ulaşlar Tourism Investments and Durable Consumer Goods Trading Inc. and Etiler Food Industry Inc., which are included in the analysis, are the companies that comply with the sustainability criteria the least. It can be said that these companies operate in the food and beverage sector more than accommodation. Unlike the others, Tek-Art Holding Inc. has been observed to comply with sustainable management and cultural environmental elements at a very low rate, but to comply with socio-economic principles at a high rate.

4.3. Findings of the Research

It was observed that all companies comply with the social and economic compliance criteria the most in terms of sustainable reporting standards, while they comply with the sustainable management criteria the least. This shows that it is difficult for many companies to comply with the corporate governance practices and roles that ultimately lead to better performance in their reports. However, it was revealed

that companies focus on issues such as water consumption, energy saving and waste management, while the least included issues are wages, compensation and work-life balance.

The research was tested with the Hausman test and analyzed using panel data analysis. The Hausman test analysis method is used to analyze how large a difference is that the sample distribution is too large to be compatible with the null hypothesis of correct determination as a function of the difference between two estimators. Since all values except the socioeconomic data are greater than 0.05, the study was continued with the random effects model.

	Chi2	Hausman Test
Sustainable	0.22	0.9941
Cultural & Environmental	2.14	0.7104
Socioeconomic	12.02	0.0172
Current Ratio	4.58	0.2057
Liquidity Ratio	1.12	0.7714
Cash Ratio	3.07	0.3810
INWCR	0.31	0.9580
Income	0.30	0.9600

Since all values except socioeconomic data are greater than 0.05, the study was continued with the random effects model.

Panel data regression models.

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	Coefficients	Rho	R squared	Wald Chi2	P Value
Current Ratio	Fixed value	2,280029	0,27328228	0,7284	17,22	0,0006
	Sustainable Management	8,214123				
	Cultural and Environmental	-13,55297				
	Socioeconomic	4,329261				
Liquidity Ratio	Fixed value	1,742447	0,20199614	0,7117	22,97	0,0000
	Sustainable Management	9,357196				
	Cultural and Environmental	-15,12104				
	Socioeconomic	4,857276				
Cash Ratio	Fixed value	1,812887	0,25922493	0,7673	15,52	0,0014
	Sustainable M.	9,909384				

	Cultural and Environmental	-12,94722				
	Socioeconomic	3,214731				
INWCR	Fixed value	4,829146	0,63848445	0,4655	7,93	0,0476
	Sustainable M.	2,922068				
	Cultural and Environmental	-1,076782				
	Socioeconomic	-3,534189				
Revenue	Fixed value	4,86 e+07	0,1920924	0,1269	0,6735	0,6735
	Sustainable M.	-9,13+e08				
	Cultural and Environmental	1,15+e09				
	Socioeconomic	2,27+e08				

When the model results are examined, since the p value is less than 0.05 in all variables except Income, we can say that the established panel regression models are statistically significant.

When the equations are examined;

- When the relationship between the Current Ratio value and 3 variables is examined (Sustainable, Cultural & Environmental and Social&Economic), it can be said that there is an inverse relationship with Cultural & Environmental (-13.55297), and a positive relationship with the other two variables (sus: 8.214123 and soci: 4.329261).
- When the relationship between the Liquidity Ratio value and 3 variables is examined (Sustainable, Cultural & Environmental and Social&Economic), it can be said that there is an inverse relationship with Cultural & Environmental (-1512104), and a positive relationship with the other two variables (sus: 9.357196 and soci: 4.857276).
- When the relationship between Cash Ratio value and 3 variables is examined (Sustainable, Cultural & Environmental and Social&Economic), it can be said that it is inversely related to Cultural & Environmental (-12.94722) and positively related to the other two variables (sus: 9.909384 and soci: 3.214731). –

When the relationship between INWCR value and 3 variables is examined (Sustainable, Cultural & Environmental and Social&Economic), it can be said that it is in positively related to Cultural & Environmental (-1.076782) and Social&Economic (-3.534189), and positively related to the other two variables (sus: 2.922068).

Conclusion

When the literature on sustainability is examined, it is seen that the importance of the concept of sustainability is increasing and theoretical studies are carried out in the context of sustainable tourism.

It is seen that the reports published by tourism companies focus on reporting and measuring according to the Turkey Sustainable Tourism Industry Criteria (TR-I) and Sustainable GRI principles.

Working capital is a value that plays a critical role in the short-term financing decisions of companies in the context of managing current assets. Efficient management of working capital is only possible with the effective use of current assets. In this study, liquidity ratios and revenues/working capital ratios measuring the efficiency of working capital and the compliance numbers of companies with corporate governance, cultural environment and socio-economic criteria in their sustainability reports were calculated using the financial statements of 9 tourism companies operating in the Borsa Istanbul tourism sector for the periods of 2017-2023. Working capital ratios were used as dependent variables and sustainability criteria compliance rates were used as independent variables.

Altın Yunus Çeşme Turistik Tesisler A.Ş., which has the highest performance among the companies, , Marmaris Altinyunus A.Ş. and Petrokent Tourism A.Ş. and the lowest performing Etiler Food Inc. and Ulaşlar Tourism Investments and Durable Consumer Goods Trade Inc. revealed the importance of the companies in the sector.

The data in the study were analyzed with the Hausman test and panel data analysis. When the model results were examined, since the p value was less than 0.05 in all variables except income, the established panel regression models were found to be statistically significant. When the relationship between the current ratio, liquidity ratio, cash ratio and income/working capital ratios used as dependent variables and the sustainable management, cultural & environmental and social & economic variables as independent variables was examined, it was revealed that the current, liquid and cash ratio and income/working capital were inversely related to Cultural & Environmental from the independent variables (Sustainable, Cultural & Environmental and Social & Economic) and positively related to the other two variables.

As a result, sustainability practices have a largely positive impact on a firm's working capital performance. However, the extent and nature of this impact may vary depending on a variety of factors, including the firm's industry, geographic location, and the characteristics of its managers. The quality and compliance of sustainability reporting can make the impact of these practices on financial performance more apparent.

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